

Quantum Exposure Index Technical Report 2026-S1: Sector-Level HNDL Exposure across 39,903 Organizations

Julio Smanioto Garcia^{*1,2}, Rafael Duarte Marcelino^{†1}, and Matheus Rufino^{‡1}

¹*GWK Security, Campinas, SP, Brazil*

²*Instituto de Física Gleb Wataghin, Universidade Estadual de Campinas (UNICAMP), Campinas, SP, Brazil*

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Abstract

Across 39,903 organizations, observed cryptographic vulnerability is high and nearly uniform across sectors. Sector-level Harvest-Now–Decrypt-Later (HNDL) exposure is driven primarily by adversarial data lifetime and migration timeline, not by large differences in observed cryptographic fragility. We consolidate the Quantum Exposure Index (IEQ) for 39,903 organizations, aggregated by sector under k -anonymity ($K = 30$), to inform post-quantum migration priorities without disclosing any individual entity. The sector ranking forms three blocks; within-sector dispersion is limited; and where public data is sparse, conservative (worst-case) scoring inflates the index. Ten recurring technical exposure archetypes appear across sectors. This report complements public TLS/PQC readiness scans [4, 10] by providing an HNDL-oriented prioritization rather than a measure of post-quantum mechanism adoption.

1 Introduction

The advent of cryptographically relevant quantum computers threatens the public-key algorithms in widespread use today, RSA (Rivest–Shamir–Adleman) and ECC (elliptic-curve cryptography). The risk is immediate even before such machines exist, because of the *harvest-now, decrypt-later* (HNDL) pattern: encrypted traffic captured today can be archived and decrypted in the future [5]. Migration to post-quantum cryptography (PQC) is therefore a risk-management priority [8, 6, 2].

Public measurement studies have begun to quantify PQC readiness on the Internet: large-scale scans of negotiated TLS (Transport Layer Security, the protocol that encrypts most Web traffic) parameters, cipher suites (the sets of cryptographic algorithms a connection negotiates), key-exchange mechanisms and certificates [4, 10]. These studies measure *adoption* of post-quantum mechanisms. They do not, by themselves, produce an HNDL *exposure* prioritization: a study can report that a domain still uses TLS 1.2 or classical key exchange, but not how urgently that organization should migrate given the lifetime of its data and its sector’s threat horizon.

*ORCID: 0009-0006-7890-5821.

†ORCID: 0009-0008-2081-6812.

‡Corresponding author: math.rufi@gmail.com. ORCID: 0000-0003-4871-5120.

The **Quantum Exposure Index (IEQ)** quantifies, per organization, exposure to this risk from observable public-facing signals [9]. This report consolidates the IEQ of **39,903 organizations**, aggregating results *by sector* to inform migration priorities without exposing any individual organization. Masking is performed by sectoral aggregation with k-anonymity ($K = 30$, a standard anonymization rule under which every published group must contain at least K organizations, so that no single one can be singled out): only sector-level statistics are published.

Quantum exposure is a broad condition: observed cryptographic fragility is high and remarkably uniform across sectors (68–71 out of 100), and 76.4% of the 39,903 organizations fall in the Critical or High exposure bands. What distinguishes sectors is therefore not how weak their cryptography is, but the *urgency of migration*, determined by the threat horizon, the data lifetime and the regulatory criticality: sectors that retain data for decades, such as health and government, accumulate greater HNDL exposure than sectors with short-lived data. Consistent with this, the sector ranking organizes into three blocks rather than a smooth gradient, while dispersion within each sector stays limited: organizations in the same sector tend to resemble one another, and the largest differences appear between sectors. Two cautions frame the results. Where public data is sparse, the model assumes the worst case, so such scores should be read as a plausible ceiling rather than a definitive measurement. And a complementary, sector-agnostic view emerges from clustering the technical signals, which yields ten recurring exposure archetypes that appear within and across sectors. The remainder of the report presents the data and methods, the global and sector-level results, the limitations and ethics of publication, and the resulting migration recommendations.

2 Data and methods

Signals are collected from each organization’s public-facing layer, through automated collection of: DNS records (the Internet’s address book, mapping domain names to the servers and mail systems behind them); TLS configuration; PQC readiness; HTTP response headers (metadata a Web server returns alongside a page, used here to check security settings); and exposed technologies (publicly visible software and server components). Data coverage is heterogeneous, averaging 68.6% of the signals in the dataset, and this coverage is incorporated into the index uncertainty. Figure 1 summarizes the resulting pipeline, from collection to the published, sector-level result.

The dataset is a 2026-S1 snapshot assembled incrementally rather than captured at a single instant. An initial cohort of about 1,400 organizations was first collected on 30 March 2026, and collection continued as the panel expanded to the full 39,903 organizations, with the most recent signals captured on 15 June 2026. Every organization carries first- and last-collection timestamps, and the analysis uses each organization’s latest available observation; the year 2026 is taken as the reference epoch (t_0) of the HNDL timeline (Figure 7). Because the window spans several weeks, posture is point-in-time within that window and signal freshness varies slightly across organizations.

The IEQ combines risk dimensions into a 0–100 score. The three dimensions reported here are Vulnerability (V), the observed cryptographic fragility (legacy families, suites susceptible to

Figure 1: From collection to publication. Automated, public-facing signals are mapped to the per-organization dimensions Vulnerability (V) and Exposure (E); combined with sector-level priors for Timeline (H) and Governance (M), they produce a per-organization IEQ score with its confidence interval. Only the last step (sector-level aggregation under $K = 30$ k-anonymity) is published in this report: no organization-level score, name, or domain appears in any output.

Shor’s algorithm [the quantum algorithm that breaks RSA- and ECC-based encryption], PQC readiness); Exposure (E), the surface and reach of exposed assets, which also includes a supplier and infrastructure dependency component (an organization’s exposure through the cloud, telecom and CDN [content-delivery network] providers it relies on); and Timeline (H), the temporal urgency given the threat horizon and the sector’s migration time. Where an organization does not declare its supplier relationships, this dependency component falls back to a sector-level prior for how structurally reliant that sector is on shared digital infrastructure. Each score carries a 90% confidence interval (CI90) estimated by Monte Carlo simulation over the input uncertainties, and the mean CI90 width per sector is reported as a robustness measure. Organizations are classified by a refined sub-sector taxonomy; sectors with fewer than 30 organizations are suppressed. Where they cannot be safely aggregated to $K = 30$, they are counted only in the global total and omitted from sector tables. No organization identifier (name or domain) is included in any output of this report [7].

V and E are complements, not substitutes: an HNDL compromise requires both a quantum-vulnerable cipher and external access to the encrypted traffic, so neither dimension alone determines risk. Rufino, Marcelino, and Garcia [9] derive this requirement from first principles, modelling attack and defense as competing constant-rate processes and showing that the resulting compromise probability is

$$P_{\text{HNDL}} = H \cdot \frac{V^a E^b}{V^a E^b + \theta}, \quad (1)$$

where θ is the ratio of defense to attack intensity, H is the probability that a cryptographically relevant quantum computer arrives within the data’s adversarial lifetime, and $a, b > 0$ are exponents capturing how strongly the attack rate responds to vulnerability and exposure, respectively.

Because V and E enter as a product rather than a sum, no fixed set of weights can reproduce this interaction: a purely additive score would treat vulnerability and exposure as substitutes, which the threat structure does not allow. The operational score published in this report follows the same multiplicative form,

$$\text{IEQ} = 100 \cdot \min(1, H \cdot V^\beta \cdot E^\gamma \cdot M), \quad (2)$$

with β and γ the elasticities (how much the score moves, in percentage terms, for a 1% change in V or E , respectively) implied by Eq. (1) and $M \geq 1$ a governance penalty multiplier for qualitative risk factors not captured by V and E (e.g., absence of a cryptographic inventory). The full derivation, axioms, and proofs are reported in [9].

In internal specification diagnostics, the multiplicative functional form of Eq. (2) performed better than the tested alternatives (CES, or constant elasticity of substitution; log-additive; and threshold forms): no alternative reproduces the interaction structure between vulnerability and exposure, which grounds the use of the product $H \cdot V^\beta \cdot E^\gamma \cdot M$ rather than a weighted sum [11]. Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.4718$ (a standard reliability statistic measuring how closely a set of items move together) is low for a reflective index but expected here, because the IEQ is a formative index: Vulnerability, Exposure and Timeline are distinct causes of risk, not manifestations of a single latent factor (one hidden, unmeasured cause) [3]. A principal-component analysis (a technique that checks whether a single underlying factor accounts for most of the variation) confirms this: the first component explains only 19.2% of the variance and 7 components are required, so there is no dominant factor; the same clustering (k-means) identifies the ten exposure archetypes discussed in the results. Sobol indices (a sensitivity-analysis measure of how much each input explains the variation in the output, including its interactions with other inputs) show high mean total effects ($V = 0.927$, $E = 0.888$), indicating strong interactions among signals consistent with the multiplicative form [1]. Finally, the Spearman correlation (a measure, from -1 to 1 , of how strongly two variables move together in rank order) between V and E is -0.0709 : weak but statistically detectable, so V and E carry mostly complementary information.

3 Results

The 39,903 organizations analyzed have a median IEQ of 76.3 (High), a mean of 68.9 and a standard deviation of 20.7, with an interdecile range (P10–P90, the gap between the 10th and 90th percentiles, i.e. excluding the most extreme 10% of organizations on each side) from 30.9 to 87.8. The mean dimension decomposition is Vulnerability (V) 69.9, Exposure (E) 60.9 and Timeline (H) 79.0, and the typical uncertainty (CI90 width) has a median of 12.4.

Figure 2 shows the global IEQ distribution. The main concentration is in the Critical and High bands, which together hold 76.4% of organizations. A smaller group sits in the Low and Minimal bands (14.8%). The band distribution (Critical 34.3%, High 42.1%, Moderate 8.8%, Low 9.9%, Minimal 4.9%) indicates a clear separation between still-exposed organizations and those with lower observed exposure.

Table 1 orders sectors by IEQ median and Figure 3 represents the same ordering with uncertainty

Figure 2: Distribution of the IEQ across the 39,903 organizations, by risk band (color). The bulk of the mass sits toward the Critical/High end (right) rather than spread evenly across the scale, with a thinner tail in the Low/Minimal bands (left).

bars (CI90). Read together, they convey not only *who* is most exposed, but *how reliable* each position is.

Table 1: Sector ranking by median IEQ. C+H % = share in Critical or High exposure; CI90 = typical width of the confidence interval of the sector median.

#	Sector	<i>n</i>	Median	Level	CI90	C+H %
1	Government / Unclassified	5,640	85.0	Critical	13.0	92.2%
2	Hospitals & health services	5,678	84.8	Critical	11.9	100.0%
3	Pharma & biotech	5,275	82.0	Critical	12.7	100.0%
4	Private health insurance	85	81.3	Critical	12.8	100.0%
5	Materials & chemicals	146	76.2	High	13.2	99.4%
6	Agribusiness	124	75.9	High	13.3	96.8%
7	Industrial manufacturing	13,434	75.0	High	13.5	98.0%
8	Defense & aerospace	35	72.8	High	13.9	97.1%
9	Utilities (energy)	530	58.2	Moderate	11.4	38.3%
10	Oil, gas & energy	100	56.8	Moderate	11.6	35.0%
11	Traditional finance	2,458	55.3	Moderate	10.2	20.8%
12	Payment processing	265	54.7	Moderate	10.3	14.7%
13	Cloud	212	39.7	Low	8.3	0.0%
14	Telecom	419	38.4	Low	6.7	0.0%
15	SaaS	3,149	30.7	Low	4.7	0.0%
16	Retail & brands (physical)	2,266	18.4	Minimal	3.1	0.0%
17	E-commerce & marketplace	68	18.1	Minimal	3.2	0.0%

The ranking spans from 85.0 (**Government / Unclassified**, top) to 18.1 (**E-commerce & marketplace**, bottom) and organizes into **three blocks**, not a smooth decline. Exact positions should be read with caution: in Figure 3 the error bars of the top sectors overlap widely. In total, **9 neighboring pairs** have overlapping CI90 intervals; exact ordering should not be interpreted as resolved. The appropriate reading is by critical block, not by individual podium. The most relevant step appears *between blocks*: the median drops from 72.8 (**Defense & aerospace**, end

Figure 3: Sector ranking of median IEQ (markers/points), with whiskers showing the 90% confidence interval (CI90) of each sector’s median. Whiskers that overlap between adjacent sectors mark positions with overlapping CI90 intervals; exact ordering should not be interpreted as resolved.

of Tier 1) to 58.2 (**Utilities (energy)**, start of Tier 2). This difference is not absorbed by the observed uncertainty.

Figure 4 explains *why* the ranking breaks into plateaus: it decomposes each sector into bands and shows that the transition is not gradual. In the **Tier 1 (critical)** sectors the bar is almost entirely red/orange: nearly 100% of organizations are Critical or High, with no lower-exposure tail. In **Tier 2 (intermediate)** (Utilities, Oil, gas & energy, Traditional finance, Payment processing), yellow (Moderate) dominates, reflecting a longer migration horizon. In **Tier 3 (lower exposure)** (Cloud, Telecom, SaaS, retail, e-commerce), the bar is green: more digital sectors, with modern TLS stacks and lower observed exposure. This separation is the main key to reading the ranking.

Figure 5 summarizes the IEQ composition by sector. The most useful reading is by column. The **Vulnerability (V)** column varies little between sectors (68–71 out of 100), indicating high and relatively homogeneous technical fragility. The main difference appears in the **Timeline (H)** column, which ranges from about 21 to 92. Since V changes little, H becomes the factor that most explains the relative position of sectors.

The uniformity of V has a concrete origin: in nearly every sector the same three signals dominate vulnerability — vulnerable internal systems, the cryptographic algorithm family in use, and vulnerable hardware security modules (HSMs) — each present in ~100% of organizations. Observed fragility is therefore *structural*, not sector-specific.

Figure 4: Risk-band composition within each sector; each bar sums to 100%. A bar dominated by a single color indicates a sector concentrated in one band, while a bar split across several colors indicates a sector with mixed exposure.

Figure 6 shows the same finding from another angle, in the **phase map**. The left panel gives context: the ellipse summarizes where most of the 39,903 organizations sit, and the boxed region marks the much narrower area where sectors (averages) cluster. The right panel zooms into that region. Two points stand out there. First, sectors line up along a narrow horizontal band, all at a similar Vulnerability level, confirming the low variation in that dimension. Second, sector colors do not follow the V/E quadrants: high- and low-IEQ sectors sit close together on the map. This shows that knowing V and E is not enough to explain final risk: the temporal dimension must also be considered.

The practical implication is direct: a sector's position in the ranking does not by itself mean it uses much weaker cryptography than the others. In many cases it indicates that the sector has less time margin. Health and government lead because they store data that may stay valuable for decades, whereas sectors such as retail and e-commerce tend to operate with shorter-lived data.

Figure 7 details dimension H through the **Harvest-Now, Decrypt-Later (HNDL)** risk. An adversary captures encrypted traffic today and attempts to decrypt it in the future, once quantum computing is viable. For each sector, the bar shows the window in which data collected in 2026 remains valuable (t_0 to $t_0 + T_D$, the adversarial lifetime). The diamond marks μ , the sector's estimated quantum-maturity year, recovered from Mosca's logistic $H = 1/(1 + e^{-k(t_0 + T_D - \mu)})$, with k a fixed slope constant [5]. The **red** segment is the part of the window after μ : data captured

Figure 5: Mean dimension decomposition by sector (all values on the 0–100 scale; warmer colors indicate higher risk). Columns V, E and H are the three input dimensions: Vulnerability (observed cryptographic fragility), Exposure (surface and reach of exposed assets) and Timeline (temporal urgency). Column Q is the combined quantum-risk core $Q = H \cdot V^\beta \cdot E^\gamma$, that is, the index before the governance multiplier M ; the published IEQ equals $100 \cdot \min(1, Q \cdot M)$. The near-constant V column set against the wide-ranging H column is the visual signature of the central finding: sector differences are driven mainly by Timeline, not by observed fragility.

Figure 6: Phase map $V \times E$. Left (context): the 1σ concentration ellipse summarizes the range of V and E observed across the 39,903 organizations; the boxed region marks where sectors actually sit. Right (zoom): the boxed region enlarged, with sectors as circles (color = median IEQ, size = number of organizations).

Figure 7: HNDL timeline by sector. Each bar spans the years during which data collected in 2026 stays strategically valuable; the diamond marks μ , the sector’s estimated quantum-maturity year. Green is the portion of that window before μ (pre-maturity window); red is the portion after μ (exposed). Longer red segments mean a larger share of today’s captured data will still be worth decrypting once the threat materializes.

today that will still be valuable when decryption becomes feasible. Health and government ($T_D \approx 20$ years) accumulate more than a decade of exposed window; retail, SaaS and e-commerce ($T_D \approx 5\text{--}6$ years) tend to have data expiring before μ .

Figure 8 carries an important reading caveat. Each point is a sector: further right means more public data could be collected about it. Sectors with lower coverage tend to show higher scores, because when information is missing the model assumes the worst case. The practical consequence is that the IEQ of little-known organizations should be read as a plausible *ceiling*, not a definitive number. Collecting more data is how the estimate is refined.

Table 2 summarizes each sector. The **P10–P90 range** measures the distance between a sector’s typical most- and least-exposed organizations. Since that range is narrow in most cases, organizations within a sector tend to resemble one another. The last two columns indicate where the reading requires caution: sectors with **lower data coverage** may be overestimated, and a high share of **atypical cases** signals profiles that merit individual review.

Transparency note. 19 organizations in very small sectors were fully suppressed. Combined, they do not reach the k-anonymity threshold ($K = 30$) even as an aggregate. They remain counted only in the global panorama and are omitted from sector tables.

Figure 8: Data coverage versus median IEQ by sector (point size proportional to the number of organizations). The downward trend — lower coverage paired with higher scores — is the visual signature of the conservative fallback described below: points further left warrant more caution than points further right.

Table 2: Sector fiche: position (median and level), internal dispersion (P10–P90 range between typical most- and least-exposed organizations), Cov. = mean data coverage and Atp. = share of organizations with an atypical profile.

Sector	Median	Level	P10–P90	Cov.	Atp.
Government / Unclassified	85.0	Critical	70.3 to 93.4	66.4%	22.7%
Hospitals & health services	84.8	Critical	75.3 to 90.2	66.0%	13.3%
Pharma & biotech	82.0	Critical	73.8 to 88.2	69.4%	18.7%
Private health insurance	81.3	Critical	72.3 to 87.7	71.0%	29.4%
Materials & chemicals	76.2	High	64.6 to 82.4	67.4%	19.2%
Agribusiness	75.9	High	65.0 to 82.2	68.5%	16.1%
Industrial manufacturing	75.0	High	64.6 to 82.3	69.1%	15.6%
Defense & aerospace	72.8	High	64.5 to 81.2	66.2%	22.9%
Utilities (energy)	58.2	Moderate	50.8 to 64.2	70.5%	24.2%
Oil, gas & energy	56.8	Moderate	49.0 to 64.5	69.0%	29.0%
Traditional finance	55.3	Moderate	49.2 to 62.2	69.0%	27.7%
Payment processing	54.7	Moderate	48.9 to 61.0	72.9%	47.2%
Cloud	39.7	Low	35.1 to 44.7	73.8%	43.4%
Telecom	38.4	Low	33.6 to 42.5	68.0%	25.1%
SaaS	30.7	Low	27.5 to 33.3	69.9%	21.3%
Retail & brands (physical)	18.4	Minimal	16.5 to 20.2	71.8%	20.2%
E-commerce & marketplace	18.1	Minimal	16.2 to 19.5	75.0%	50.0%

Beyond the per-sector reading, we apply unsupervised clustering to the 13 observed technical signals using k-means (a method that groups organizations into k clusters of similar signal profiles), with $k = 10$ and a silhouette score of 0.2719 (a measure, from -1 to 1 , of how well-separated those clusters are). This score should be read as evidence of recurring profiles, not sharply separated natural classes. The goal is to identify organizations with similar combinations of signals, regardless of their sector. The result is **10 recurring exposure profiles**, labeled archetypes **A to J**.

Each archetype is a pattern of technical posture, not a sector category. Table 3 reports how many organizations fell into each group, which macro-family appears most frequently within it, and the mean IEQ of those organizations. Figure 9 complements the reading by showing how sectors distribute across archetypes.

Table 3: Catalogue of exposure archetypes (k-means over the 13 signals). The “predominant macro-family” column reports the broad sector *family* from which most members of the cluster originate (e.g. “Critical industry” groups manufacturing, materials, defense and related sectors; “Health” groups hospitals, pharma and health insurance). These macro-families are the clustering origin, not rows of the sector ranking in Table 1.

Archetype	n	%	Predominant macro-family	Mean IEQ	Level
A	8,325	20.9%	Critical industry	73.7	High
B	3,808	9.5%	Health	77.7	High
C	3,811	9.6%	Health	65.7	High
D	3,916	9.8%	Critical industry	68.0	High
E	3,709	9.3%	Critical industry	63.8	High
F	6,639	16.6%	Health	74.4	High
G	3,050	7.6%	Critical industry	63.0	High
H	2,064	5.2%	Critical industry	61.1	High
I	3,114	7.8%	Critical industry	56.5	Moderate
J	1,467	3.7%	Critical industry	66.7	High

The main result is that archetypes do not map directly onto sectors. A sector may concentrate more organizations in a given archetype, but no sector appears as a single block. In practice, different modes of exposure coexist within the same sector. The per-sector analysis indicates priority and urgency; the per-archetype analysis reveals technical patterns that recur within and across sectors. The signals that most differentiate the archetypes are mostly everyday web-security hygiene controls, such as enforcing secure browser connections and basic domain protections. Cryptographic weaknesses, such as outdated encryption protocols and algorithms known to be breakable by future quantum computers, appear in some profiles but are not the main axis of separation between archetypes. This mirrors the dimension analysis above: cryptographic fragility is high and relatively uniform, while everyday web-security hygiene varies more between organizations.

A sector’s own score is not the whole picture, because organizations do not operate in isolation: many depend on a small number of shared providers, such as cloud platforms, telecom carriers and content-delivery networks. This is the practical meaning of **blast radius**: a sector can show a low IEQ on the strength of its own observable signals and still be exposed if it leans heavily on a provider, or a class of providers, with a weaker cryptographic posture. The dependency component described in Data and methods is a structural, sector-level approximation of this risk, used precisely because individual supplier relationships are not observable from public-facing

Figure 9: Archetype composition (%) within each sector. A row dominated by a single color is technically homogeneous; a row spread across several archetypes mixes multiple exposure profiles, evidence that archetypes cut across sector boundaries rather than align with them.

signals. A favorable position in the ranking should therefore be read as a statement about an organization's own posture, not as a guarantee that every link in its supply chain is equally well positioned.

4 Limitations and ethics

Public-facing signals are not a complete cryptographic inventory; they approximate an organization's externally observable posture. The IEQ is accordingly a prioritization score, not a calibrated breach probability. Missing data can increase conservative (worst-case) scores, so low-coverage estimates should be read as a ceiling rather than a direct measurement, and sector labels are themselves approximations derived from an automated taxonomy.

The dataset is also a point-in-time panel collected between 30 March and 15 June 2026; it reflects observable posture during that window and is not a continuous monitoring feed.

The model further assumes that an organization's cryptographic posture and its external exposure are approximately independent across the population, an assumption documented in the underlying structural framework [9]. This assumption is most likely to fail within tightly integrated supply chains, where an organization's posture correlates with that of the providers it depends on. The blast-radius dependency component described in Data and methods is a partial, structural mitigation for this: a sector-level prior, not a measured map of actual supplier relationships. It does not replace a dedicated third-party risk assessment of an organization's specific vendors.

Finally, no exploit attempts were performed; collection is limited to public-facing signals. No individual organization is named or ranked, and results are published only in aggregate, under

k-anonymity ($K = 30$). The report is intended to support migration prioritization, not attribution or public shaming.

5 Recommendations

Post-quantum migration should be prioritized in a structured way. In the dataset, 76.4% of organizations are in Critical or High exposure, and observed cryptographic fragility is high across all sectors. The central management decision is the migration order, which here is better explained by Timeline (H) than by Vulnerability (V), since V discriminates little between sectors.

Tier 1, which should act now, comprises Government / Unclassified, Hospitals & health services, Pharma & biotech, Private health insurance, Materials & chemicals, Agribusiness, Industrial manufacturing, and Defense & aerospace: public or regulated sectors with long-lived data and limited migration margin. For this tier we recommend an immediate cryptographic inventory, prioritization of harvest-now (long-validity) data, and a PQC transition plan with semi-annual targets.

Tier 2, which should plan, comprises Utilities (energy), Oil, gas & energy, Traditional finance, and Payment processing, all showing intermediate exposure; these sectors should establish a PQC roadmap and crypto-agility (the ability to swap cryptographic algorithms without major system rework) before the next cycle.

Tier 3, which should maintain and monitor, comprises Cloud, Telecom, SaaS, Retail & brands (physical), and E-commerce & marketplace, with lower modeled HNDL urgency; the priority here is to consolidate crypto-agility and watch for regressions.

Across all tiers, the priority is to improve data coverage and cryptographic asset inventories, so that conservative scoring is progressively replaced by direct measurement.

As a final caveat, in sectors with sparse public data, part of the score reflects the model's worst-case assumption rather than direct measurements; collect more data before irreversible decisions in those cases. The index is statistically validated (see Data and methods), but it serves to *triage and prioritize*. It does not replace an individual technical audit.

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